

D7.1 – HORUS Communication Tools

Project Information

Project Full Title	Casting light on HOst-cytomegaloviRUs interaction in Solid organ Transplantation
Project Acronym	HORUS
Call	HORIZON-HLTH-2021-DISEASE-04
Start date of the project	1 November 2022
Duration	60 Months
Project Coordinator	Hannah Kaminski, Associate Professor, MD PhD
Project Website	https://www.horus-project.eu/

Deliverable Information

Deliverable n°	D7.1
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WP n°	7
Lead Beneficiary	UBx
Type	DEC
Due Date	2023-02-28
Submission Date	2023-03-31

Dissemination Level

PU	Public	X
SEN	Sensitive	

Document Log

Version	Date	Author	Description of Change
V1	2023-03-28	Stéphanie Grégoire (UBx)	Final draft

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1 Executive Summary

Communication tools were prepared by ESOT, assisted by UBx. ESOT proposed different items (logo, brochures, PowerPoint, templates...) for strategic communication and HORUS project's visibility. Each beneficiary shall ensure that the results are promoted according to the project's strategic messages and using the Logo. The structured deliverable templates and guidelines for HORUS branding will be sent to all partners and will be stored on UBCloud (<https://ubcloud.u-bordeaux.fr>).

High-quality, non-confidential information will be shared through social media and on the consortium's website.

2 HORUS Branding

2.1 Logo

Primary logo

Main logo

Clear space

Alternative logos

2.2 Colour palette

Primary colours

TEAL C81 M15 Y57 K2 R0 G153 B153 #009999	YELLOW C0 M29 Y100 K0 R255 G204 B0 #ffc000	ORANGE C0 M50 Y100 K0 R255 G153 B51 #ff9933	RUST C27 M79 Y94 K15 R153 G51 B0 #993300
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Secondary colours

BLACK C0 M0 Y0 K100 R0 G0 B0 #000000	GREY C0 M0 Y0 K30 R179 G179 B179
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The following colours are to be used to create strong brand recognition and leave a lasting impression. It is suggested to select teal + another primary colour as the focus of any one material. The remaining colours should be used sparingly for highlights, graphs and callouts.

2.3 Colour and Logo combinations

The colour of the main image highlight determines which logo should be used. Teal must always be one of the two colours-used on cover images.

2.4 Typography

Proxima Nova Bold (titles, headings and key messages)

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk
 Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu
 Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz 0123456789 ?!&%

Proxima Nova Regular Italic (used sparingly in body copy)

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk
 Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu
 Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz 0123456789 ?!&%

Arial Regular (on-screen body copy)

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk
 Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu
 Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz 0123456789 ?!&%

Proxima Nova Regular (body copy)

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk
 Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu
 Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz 0123456789 ?!&%

Proxima Nova Light (intro text and quotes)

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk
 Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu
 Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz 0123456789 ?!&%

Arial Regular (on-screen titles and headings)

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk
 Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu
 Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz 0123456789 ?!&%

Primary typeface

Proxima Nova is the primary typeface for all HORUS materials. The font is available for users with access to Adobe Creative Cloud via Adobe TypeKit and is licence-free.

Digital: Arial should be used for all digital materials produced using any of the Microsoft programmes. Arial is a system font and is universally compatible for all users regardless of their computer's operating system.

2.5 Imagery

2.5.1 Primary Imagery

All primary images should depict operating room procedures in black and white. A portion of the image should be highlighted in one of the primary colours. This is achieved by setting the overlay colour to multiply.

2.5.2 Supporting Imagery

All supporting imagery should depict medical instruments, equipment or anatomy models. These should be black and white photographs, set to multiply and appear on a solid colour background.

2.6 Hieroglyphs

Simplified depictions of the supporting imagery may be used alongside the images.

These should always be black and constructed using circles and lines.

2.7 Icons

The use of icons is encouraged to accompany materials that are particularly text heavy.

All icons created must adhere to the following:

- Simplistic in style and level of detail

- Identical line thickness
- Rounded corners

- Similar height / width

The icons shown are for guidance purposes only.

2.8 Example Layouts

2.8.1 Brochure

2.8.2 Roller banners

2.8.3 Web banners

2.8.4 PowerPoint

The main presentation slides must be kept to the two colour pairing rule.

All colours may be used for graphs, callout boxes and section break pages.

3 HORUS templates

3.1 Letterhead template

3.2 Deliverable template

HORUS ○○○○ Title of deliverable

Dx.y – title of deliverable – vXX

Project Information

Project Full Title	Castling light on hOst o u t o m e p a t i o n i n t e r a c t i o n i n S o l i d o r g a n T r a n s p l a n t a t i o n
Project Acronym	HORUS
Call	HORIZON-HLTH-2021-DISEASE-04
Start date of the project	1 November 2022
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HORUS ○○○○ Title of deliverable

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HORUS ○○○○ Title of deliverable

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HORUS ○○○○ Title of deliverable

1 Executive Summary

2 Title 1

2.1 Title 2

Text...

2.1.1.1.1 Title 3

Text...

2.1.1.2 Title 4

Text...

2.1.1.2.1 Title 5

Text... hyperlink@xxxxxxxx

Use automated cross-references to tables (Table 1) and figures (Figure 1) and bibliography Error
Reference source not found.

Table 1 table title

Header 1	Header 2
text	text
text	text
text	text

Figure 1 xxxxx.

Numbered list example:

- 1) Text
i)
- 2) Text
i)

Dotted list example:

- Text
o
- Text
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3 References

Include references in this section using the following style:
[1] Authors, Title, Journal, Vol. (Issue), year, pp.

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4 HORUS Website and Social Medias

The HORUS project website (<https://www.horus-project.eu/>) and social media platforms such as LinkedIn (https://www.linkedin.com/company/horus_euproject/) and Twitter ([@HORUS_EUproject](https://twitter.com/HORUS_EUproject)), are the main tools for disseminating information about the consortium and the achievements of the project, providing visitors with comprehensive information about its context and objectives. The HORUS website's details can be found in another deliverable entitled D7.7 "HORUS Website".